

ROLE OF TRADITIONAL CRAFT EMBROIDERIES IN EMPOWERING AND ELEVATING INDIAN WOMEN: IMPLEMENTING TRADITIONAL CRAFT EMBROIDERY IN GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

India is known for its rich tradition of art and craft. Diverse heritage of craft embroideries is found in India which differ from places to places, like Kashida is found in Kashmir, Chikankari is popular in Uttar Pradesh, Kantha is famous in Bengal, Phulkari is from Punjab, Kasuti is speciality of Karnataka etc. In India huge proportion of population is dependent on art and craft for their livelihood. Craft embroidery is extensively used in generating income specially by the women of the society.

It is very unfortunate to state that in a country like India, in some sections of the society, gender discrimination is prevailing. Girl child is not getting proper education as compared to their male siblings which results in lower literacy levels of girls and hence unemployment. That is why they are dependent on the male family members for their livelihood.

The Present study deals with the implementation of Traditional craft embroideries in Government girl's schools as an initiative to empower the future women of the country. By implementing traditional craft embroidery in girl's Government schools, we not only promote our old traditional craft, but will also open a new source of income for girls which will help to empower them.

Keywords: *Traditional Craft, Embroidery, Women Empowerment, Shadow work Embroidery, Outline Embroidery.*

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Introduction

In India Traditional craft industry is the industry of imagination, innovation, and creation. This is the industry of future as they are important contributing factors to the employment and economic growth. Indian craft is having a special place in the world. Handwoven Indian textiles flaunts on the foreign fashion shows, handmade Indian carpets covers most of the elegant floors in the world. The craftsman and craftswomen learn these skills from their ancestors as a legacy.

Traditional craft are the cultural heritage of India which reflects the culture and tradition of particular region. Some crafts have regional specialities, like the techniques used, motifs and materials used makes them distinct in itself.

Importance of traditional craft embroideries

Traditional craft embroideries have special cultural as well as economical significance in India as these craft have not only special historical significance but they are equally important for the growth of the economy of the country. As the products created using traditional craft embroideries are in huge demand in foreign markets and account for increase in Indian exports. The traditional craft embroidery is creating various job opportunities for women and making them financially independent. It is important to learn traditional embroidery craft not only for the tradition and culture, however, but it also helps in generating foreign exchange as in embroidery work indigenous raw materials are required (**Guridi et al. 2021**).

The world is fascinated with the traditional craft embroideries of India and the creativity produced through the various embroidery works. In the embroidery works, the local resources, skills, and initiatives are used. Traditional craft embroideries are the results of years of unconscious experiment and evolution. Craft skills are transferred from generation to generation as a legacy, from forefather to sons and to grandsons. There are variations in the embroidery crafts in different communities in India and they get refined by passage of time.

The prime importance of the traditional craft embroideries has been met to individual's requirements and communities (**Schauer 2017**). Craft embroidery add colour, texture and richness to the products and they are used to communicate the rich culture and tradition of particular region. People get to know about the speciality of a particular region through embroidery products.

Traditional Craft embroidery is a major source of export for India and generate huge

export revenue. The outfits created using craft embroideries are in huge demand in western countries.

According to **Jha (2019)**, crafting that is done through traditional embroidery is always unique and the attires of embroidery work always have versatility crafting that differentiates the people from the other people.

Types of Indian embroidery

Indian traditional embroideries can be classified on the basis of their motifs, designs, colours, technique and region of production (**Tiwari, A, 2017**). On the basis of region, few very famous embroideries are *Kashida*, *Chikankari*, *Kasuti*, *Phulkari*, *Zari*, *Kantha* etc. *Kashida* or formally known as *kashidakari* is found in Kashmir, *Chikankari* is popular in Uttar Pradesh, *Kantha* is famous in Bengal, *Phulkari* is from Punjab, *Kasuti* is speciality of Karnataka etc.

Figure 1 Various types of embroidered crafts
Source: Panda 2020, p.987)

1. Kashidakari (Kashmir): *Kashidakari* is the oldest form of embroidery that originated in Jammu and Kashmir. Colour, texture, designs and techniques are the most eye-centric

Figure 2: *Kashidakari* Embroidery

reasons for this type of traditional embroidered craft. This kind of crafting was started in the 15th century during the period of the Sultan-Zain-ul-Abidin. In this phase, *Kashida* embroidery work was started and weaving techniques were brought from Persia and Turkistan. *Kashidakari* motifs that are used in embroidery are inspired the natural flora and fauna of Kashmir. Vines, birds, leaves and flowers are mostly used as motifs and that is the most

defining aspect of this form of embroidery. Embroidery is mostly done on Wool, Cotswold, cotton, and silk wool.

According to McGowan (2021), Kashida embroideries are popular for using pastel colours and these designs are found in the shade of white and light colours. The Kashida crafts are designed to make shawls and are very popular in the cottage industry of Srinagar. Main stitches used in Kashida embroidery are Satin Stitch, Talbar, Chain Stitch, Darning Stitch, and Stem Stitch. The specialty of these designs is that they offer a flat appearance of the single thread in the design. Kashmir shawls, sarees, and other dress materials become more attractive due to the Kashida embroidery craft.

2. Chikankari (Uttar Pradesh): The word ‘Chikan’ is derived from Persian word

Figure 3 Chikankari Embroidery

‘Chakin’ which means delicate pattern over fabric. Chikankari is one of the most famous Indian embroidery arts practiced in Uttar Pradesh. Lucknow is known as the hub of chikankari embroidery (Chuchyaha 2020). In the Chikankari embroidered wrong side of the fabric creates a shadow on the right side and this kind of embroidered crafting is also known as shadow work. Another name for chicken embroidery is white embroidery as it was essentially practiced with the white fabric on white cloth. In today's time, it is practiced on various types of fabrics such as cotton, georgette, nylon, and linen. The most common embroidered crafts are bed sheets, curtains, pillow covers, and table cloths and cushion cover. This embroidered crafting is used on various pastel colours; however, the white colour thread was used for this embroidered craft. Jasmine, peacock, rose, parrot and lace patterns are common designs embroidered in the Chikankari embroidery. Satin

stitch, Backstitch, Stem stitch, and buttonhole stitch are used to stitch the embroidered design. Flat style and knotted embossed are the most common types of chikankari works. These kinds of works are done on the kurta, sari, and ladies' blouses (**Lentis 2017**).

3. Kantha (Bengal): Kantha is the traditional embroidery craft practiced in Bengal and its literal meaning is patched clothes. The oldest form of kantha dates back in 1800. This kind of embroidery is done on sari and dhoti. The embroidery is done by using white thread. Grey, white or black sari are used for this kind of embroidery work. Two types of

Figure 4 Kantha Embroidery

Kantha embroidery are done in Bengal. In the first type dhoti and sarees are piled up on top of each other and get embroidered. In the second type of embroidery, Tussar silk thread is used to do pictorial embroidery on the cotton bed sheet. Solar, moon, lotus, Swastik, wheel, tree of life, and Kalka designs are used to print on the embroidered craft. Old clothes are used to draw this

kind of embroidery works and discarded colourful borders of the sarees are used to design the embroidered craft. Running, loop, darning stitch, and satin are the stitches used for stitching the designs (**Sharma et al. 2020**)

4. Phulkari (Punjab): Phulkari is the traditional embroidery craft practiced in Punjab and it was started in the 15th century. Phulkari is the combination of two words phul and Kari that means flower work. The floral work in the shawls is decorated with a flower design. It is the traditional embroidered shawls of Punjab designed for the women to cover their heads in the gurdwara. Phulkari embroidered shawls are the significance of happiness and prosperity of the Punjab culture. In the earlier period, phulkari

Figure 5 Phulkari Embroidery

embroidery was done on the back cover however, it has been now done to bolster cover, cushion covers, and saris. This kind of embroidery is done on the wrong side with the threads of floss silk. Rayon floss and blended threads are used for designing the embroidered crafts. Horizontal, vertical, and diagonal stitching are done on this kind of embroidered product (Ata-Ullah et al. 2020).

5. Zari Work: Zari is the most traditional embroidered craft practiced in India. It is also known as Zardosi embroidery. Zari embroidery is the craft of gold embroidery on fabrics. Golden and silver thread are used for embroidered crafting. Metal thread is practicing mostly in Surat and Varanasi and metal threading is also known as Kalabathi. In the traditional period, it was done on silk. The embroidering crafting of zari is difficult and complex design was deigned through using golden and silver threads with studded pearls and precious stone. Two types of Zari embroidery is done heavy zaridosi and light zoridosi. In the heavy zaridosi precious stone and gems are designed while in the light zaridosi light pearls and stone are used to magnify the work. Jali, Bharat designs, floral designs, birds, and animals are the five main types of designs that are embroidered during this crafting. Salma Sitara, kamdani, monkish, minakari, and gota are the popular style in this kind of embroidered crafting (Porko et al. 2018).

Figure 7 Zardozi Work

Figure 7 Zardozi Work

6. Kasuti (Karnataka): Kasuti is the traditional embroidery art form of Karnataka women. Traditions, profession, and customs of Karnataka are symbolized through the Kasuti embroidery art. Kasuti is the combination of two words kai and suti which means hand weaved. Kasuti is the handwork embroidered with the help of cotton thread. Chandrakalisari is the most famous sari which was designed with the Kasuti work. Elena,

Figure 8 Kasuti Embroidery

seragu, kulai, kusuba, and lunch are the five garments on which Kasuti work is embroidered. Mycological and architectural flora and fauna are represented on the embroidered design of Kasuti. Bird motifs such as peacock, parrot, and squirrel are embroidered on the garments. Rudraksha, anklets, flower pots, chess square, and cradle inspire the Kasuti embroidery (Gravina 2019).

7. ChambaRumal (Himachal Pradesh): Chambais one of the most beautiful and exceptional embroidered crafts of Himachal Pradesh. Fine and flawless works of the needle are done to design the embroidered craft. These types of embroidered work are done on the lehenga to make it more beautiful. Designs and motifs in traditional chamba embroidery have deep rooted cultural significance. The ladies of the royal families used to embroider *therumals* in their free time as a pass time activity. The production of embroidered *rumals* became so abundant in Chamba that the geographical denomination ChambaRumal became almost a synonym for the embroidery in the entire Himachal Pradesh. (Aryan 1976).

In Chamba embroidery, untwisted silk threads are used on cotton fabrics of high thread count for fine workmanship. Double sided stitches (long and short stitches), satin stitches, running stitch, cross stitch, button hole stitch and herringbone stitches are the common type of stitches used in ChambaRumals.

Figure 9 Chamba Rumal

8. Applique Embroidery (Orrissa)- Appliqué is a French term which is used to describe a technique by which the decorative effect is obtained by super-imposing patches of coloured fabrics on a base fabric, the edges of the patches being sewn on some form of stitchery. It is a sustainable form of art in which the artisan or the workers make use of old, torn, not usable, clothes and apparels.

In this process, the pieces of fabric are collected from the tailors and export houses that are of no use them and their designs are drawn on them by using the cloth chalk. The designs are then cut and stitched to other fabric by stitching them with hand or using embroidery machines resulting in the development of beautiful and creative designs on the new cloth which is used to make products like coin pouch, bag, shoes, lamp, table mats, others.

Applique craft like other crafts is also a popular craft with a high employment potential and a flourishing market.

Figure 10 Applique Embroidery

Summary of different types of embroidery practised in different regions

Region	Name of Embroidery	Embroidery Techniques	Types of designs
Jammu Kashmir	Kashida	Outline embroidery	Flaura and fauna, Butterfly, and fruit designs are embroidered on the fabric
Uttar Pradesh	Chikenkari	Shadow embroidery	Rose, parrot, peacock, and jasmine are designed on the fabric
Bengal	Kantha	Patchwork embroidery	Lotus, Swastik, moon, solar, wheel, and kayak are embroidered on the fabric
Punjab	Phulkari	Outline	Rose and flowers are embroidered in

		embroidery	the various square, rectangle, and triangle shape.
Surat and Varanasi	Zari	Outline embroidery	Floral designs, jari, flowers, and birds are designed on this kind of embroidered work.
Karnataka	Kasuti	Fish Scale embroidery	Peacock, parrot, squirrel, and old temple are embroidered on the fabric
Himachal Pradesh	Chamba	Candle wicking embroidery	Small birds, fruits, and flowers
Orissa	Applique	Patchwork with running, hemming or button hole stitch	Geometrical motifs, birds ,fruits, flowers ,leaves or any inspired motifs

Table 1: Summary of different types of embroidery practised in different states with the techniques and designs used

Implementation of traditional craft embroideries in Girls Government schools

From, the ancient times, craft embroidery is perceived as the art made for women. Craftswomen from rural India are involved in designing craft embroidery as a part of the legacy of their community. Now a days, Craft embroidery is seen as a source employment. Implementing traditional craft embroideries in the girl’s government school is one step closer to empowering the women and enabling them to be financially independent.

In a patriarchal society like India, where some sections of society, are in the grip of gender discrimination. Girls are not given formal education and hence their literacy rate is lower as compared to boys.

Educating the girls about traditional craft embroideries will not only elevate the lives of girls but that will also help to enhance the economy of the country as products created using traditional craft embroidery are exported to the different parts of the world. According to **Medkova 2017**, Implementation of traditional craft embroideries helps the government to bring more and more girls to school. The parents will send girls to the

government school where they can get an education and also learn the various types of craft embroidery.

Importance of implementing traditional craft embroideries in the girl's government school: Implementing traditional craft embroideries in the girl's government school is important from many aspects as :

- (a) It helps the government to increase the literacy rate of women and enhance women empowerment in the country.
- (b) Implementation of traditional craft embroideries in the girl's government school will promote our old culture and tradition and it will also open new vistas for girls.
- (c) Girls can become more powerful by learning the traditional embroidery crafting with the modern education in the school.
- (d) Teaching traditional embroidery crafting to female students provides them a better opportunity to represent their talent. In the government school, the government provides them an opportunity to learn and develop their crafting skills and get a platform to show their talent (**Deka 2019**).
- (e) Implementation of traditional embroidery crafting will provide various advantages to the girl's students such as help in learning the essential core values, cultivate creativity and ingenuity, skills will help in adulthood, open job opportunity and helps in learning the value of money with embroidery.

Developing essential core values: Craft embroidery is our ancient tradition and implementation of embroidery crafting in the girl's government school will help to develop core values regarding the tradition among the girl's students. The implementation of traditional embroidery crafting in the government girls' school is a good initiative to emphasize the traditional culture and an initiative to keep the tradition alive (**Spieler et al. 2020**).

Cultivates creativity and ingenuity: Traditional embroidery crafts is about developing creativity among the girls' children and making them powerfully creative and innovative. Traditional embroidery crafting uses various DIY which means that girls children used the old material and decorate those materials with various kinds of embroidery. Implementation of embroidery crafting in the school makes them more innovative.

Open job opportunity: Learning the traditional embroidery craft opens various job opportunities for the girl's students and they can become more powerful and generate a major source of income (**Nicholas 2018**).

Essentials for the implementation of traditional craft embroideries in Girls Government School

To implement the traditional craft embroidery in the school, the government should focus on various things.

- Traditional embroideries crafts vary from the region to region and the embroidery work of every region has its own importance. Government should keep proper trainers to guide the girl's students for embroidery crafts. Teachers who are skilled in embroidery should teach the girl's student regarding the various embroideries craft such as chickenkari, phulkari, and many more.
- Government should influence the parents to send their girl child to the school where they can learn the traditional embroidery craft along with the studies (**Kokko et al. 2020**). The government programmer should highlight the job opportunities for the girls in the field of embroideries crafting.
- All the necessary items needed for the embroidery work such as fabrics, needles, thread, and colours and the weaving machine should be provided to every female student in the government school. It will develop interest among the parents to send their girl child to a school where they can get an education with the skills of embroidered crafts.

Successful implementation of traditional craft embroidery in girls school will led to following advantages:

- The rate of girls' education will increase in the school due to the implementation of traditional craft embroidery.
- Girls' student will get more options to choose their careers in the field of embroidery crafting. This will raise their contribution to the country's economy.
- The involvement of girls in the embroidered crafting helps in reducing poverty in the country.
- The GDP of the unorganized sector through the traditional embroidered crafting will increase by the involvement of women (**Pllanen and Urdzina 2017**).

Conclusion

Men and women jointly bear the burden of society. The transition will not be smooth if one of the wheels is big and the other is small. In order to smoothly run the society and to maintain the social and economic balance, it is important to have equal position of men and women in the society and it is equally important to educate both of them.

The implementation of traditional craft embroidery in girl's government schools is the best initiative by the government to encourage women to be independent and contribute to the country's economy. Various types of embroidered crafting are practicing in the various state of the country. Traditional embroidered crafting is the needle works done on a particular type of fabrics with some specification. Embroidered crafting is the representation of tradition and culture of a particular region. The designs of embroidery represent the people believe and faith in specific things. The embroidered crafting has a major role in boosting up the exports of the economy.

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